

On the issue of continuity between the Veneti and the Slovenes

written by

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Abstract

The classical Venetic theory that appeared in the eighties advocated the presence of the Slovenes (in German traditionally referred to by the signifier *Windisch*) in areas South of the Danube long before the sixth century, when, according to the dominant scenarios of academic thought, these areas were first settled by the proto-Slavs. The classical Venetic theory was rejected by the linguistic, historiographic and archaeological sciences and since then it has been considered a pseudo-scientific thought. The aim of this paper is to present to the international professional and general public the latest development in the Venetic theory; it is therefore an updated, critique considering, version of the Venetic theory on the origins of the Slovenes and other ethnic Slavs. With it, by the application of a set of formal-analytic and discursive-analytic methods of reading of sources in the ethno-symbolic approach to the understanding of nationality, and within the concept of hegemony the role of political sciences in the science of the ethnogenesis of the Slavs has been determined. In this paper the power of the (counter-hegemonic) argument prevails over the argument of (hegemonic) power, as the attribution of the Venetic ethnonym to the corpus of inscriptions of the Atestine archaeological culture has been legitimately dismissed, and consequently the theory of the sixth century settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs, i.e. the Veneti, in the areas between the Adriatic and the Danube has been rejected. The paper serves as an act of counter-hegemony in the Slovene historiography and memory studies.

Keywords: Early Slavs, Sclaveni, Veneti, Venetic theory, hegemony, Slovenes

Introduction

In the year 551 the Gothic historian Jordanes wrote: “/.../ beginning at the source of the Vistula, the populous race of the Venethi dwell, occupying a great expanse of land. Though their names are now dispersed amid various clans and places, yet they are chiefly called Sclaveni and Antes” (*Getica* 5).¹ This paper follows Jordanes’s tradition of equating between the Veneti and the Sclaveni, from which the Venetic theory grows. In the first part, it deals with placing the issue of continuity between the ancient Veneti and modern Slovenes into the proper theoretical frame of ethno-symbolism and (counter)hegemony. In the second part, it analyzes in this framework the relevant ancient statements about the Veneti and late-antiquity statements about the Sclaveni. Through this structure three claims are rejected: 1) on the early medieval settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs; 2) on the ethnic dissimilarity between the Baltic and the Adriatic branch of the ancient Veneti; 3) on the identification of the Adriatic Veneti of antiquity with the Atestine archaeological culture of the ancient Northern Adriatic.

This last point is perhaps the most significant content of the research. The Atestine archaeological culture had produced inscriptions in a Northern variant of the Etruscan script. The language of these inscriptions is considered Venetic by the ethnogenetic discourses of the ideological apparatuses of Slovenia (and of other states). It is likewise considered Venetic by the classical Venetic theory (Bor et al. 1989). Concerning the naming there is no disagreement between the two poles (on the contrary, there is consensus, therefore hegemony). Given that the classical Venetic theory derives the Slovenes from the ancient Adriatic Veneti and given that it considers the language of the Atestine archaeological culture as Venetic, it is understandable that it tries (unsuccessfully) to read the inscriptions of this culture through Slovene.

¹ Mierow 1908.

Thesis and methodology

This paper is written in the tradition of understanding not explaining. Its basic thesis is accordingly appropriate, as it reads as follows:

Between the referentiality in the dispersion of ancient written statements about the Veneti, and the referentiality in the dispersion of written statements about the Sclaveni from the epoch between the 4th and the 7th centuries there is an obvious continuity concerning the activated motives.

Methods of formal analysis of primary (and secondary) sources combined with methods of discursive analysis have been used while researching this thesis. Primary sources have been analyzed with the formal-linguistic method to determine the meaning of texts in Greek or Latin and to set the appropriate meaning while citing their content in English. E.g. it was found that the term “Northern pillar” (*stela boreios*) in Pseudo-Scymnus is no other than the mythical Pillar of Atlas, which implies the North of the European continent and not the Alps or any other area. Similarly, the phrase “*ethne megista*” cannot signify a “small ethnicity” except in a conscious decision for oppositional reading (more below). Simultaneously, the sources have been analyzed with the formal-logical method, which tests the logical appropriateness of the obtained results by the method of linguistic analysis. So, the reasoning that sources which speak of the Baltic Veneti represent in fact the Sclaveni appears as founded, given that to the contrary the Slavs disappear completely from the ancient written sources, which doesn’t seem very logical considering they are the Europe’s largest ethnicity. Historical analysis of primary sources deals with the placing of the source in the context of its occurrence. Through this analysis the claims of unauthenticity of the writings of Moses Khorenatsi or of St. Caesarius of Nazianzus are rejected, as the unauthenticity of these sources had been determined purely as the result of their reference to the Sclaveni prior to the alleged sixth century settlement, exactly the settlement this paper challenges.

The methods of archaeology of knowledge and genealogy have also been used. Archaeology of knowledge offers an understanding of the discursive formation of the object through statements that were actually stated about it; it doesn’t deal with the origin of the object, but rather with its emergence. Through the archaeology of knowledge it is possible to determine how the relocations of individual mythical elements have influenced the considerations on the locations of the Veneti, e.g. how the replacement of the “amber Phaethon” by “Hesiod’s Phaethon” has shifted the location of the Veneti in some statements. Genealogy focuses on power relations and the subsequent use of language in a concrete epoch and space; it deals with bodies, with how they are controlled and disciplined through power relations set by a discourse. With genealogy we may determine how the power of the declarant in the form of Julius Caesar played a key role in the construction of the Armorican Veneti as a separate branch of the Veneti; or how the formation of the region Venetia (et Histria), reaching the river Po, under Octavian had influenced, due to his power, the subsequent considerations and declarations about the Adriatic Veneti.

While facing the Atestine epigraphy, the paleographic method of reading has been used in accordance with paleographic rules, described in the book *La lingua venetica* (Pellegrini and Prodocimi 1967), which allowed working hypotheses to be set on the appearance of collective names on these inscriptions and the comparison of these collective names with known names in Greek and Latin to be made, the purpose of which was to determine, which names appear most often on the Atestine inscriptions. Namely, it seems probable, that this most frequent naming is in fact the self-naming of the people that had created these inscriptions.

With the use of this methodology it turns out that the above-stated basic thesis is fully confirmed. Over ten motives that appear in the ancient statements about the Veneti and then reappear in the statements about the Sclaveni, have been identified. One such motive is the motive of the sacred river: the Eridanus in statements about the Veneti by Pseudo-Scylax (*Periplus* 19),² Euripides (*Hippolytus* 735-741),³ Polybius (*History* 2, 16; 2, 17),⁴ etc. plays symbolically the same role as the Phison in the statement about the Sclaveni of St. Caesarius of Nazianzus (*Four Dialogues* 2, 110).⁵ Similarly, the motive of the lyre as the musical instrument of peace, the playing on which protects a man from the dangers of politics or war, is repeated. In statements on the Veneti this motive can be found in *Punica* by Silius Italicus (*Punica* 12, 212-221),⁶ while in statements about the Sclaveni the same motive reappears in Theophylact Simocatta (*History* 6, 2, 10-16).⁷ The motive of the white horse also appears, in statements about the Veneti we find it in Strabo (*Geography* 5, 1, 9),⁸ while in statements about the Sclaveni this motive appears as the animal of the deities *Svarožič*, *Svetovid*, *Jarilo* etc., respectively. Another such motive is the sacred tree; in statements about the Veneti these are the Heliades / *aigeiroi* (black poplars), while in statements about the Sclaveni this role is taken by the linden tree; in this regard Hesychius informs us that it is symbolically the same tree, as he equates the meaning of the words “*aigeiroi*” and “*tiliai*” in his *Alphabetical Collection of All Words*.⁹ Other motives that appear in statements about the Veneti as well as in statements about the Sclaveni are: a national curse (on the Veneti / Paphlagonians in Aristophanes (*Knights* 1-84),¹⁰ on the Sclaveni in Ioannes of Ephesus (*Historia Ecclesiastica* 3, 3, 25)),¹¹ the smashing of the head against the rock (in the context of Veneti in Euripides (*Hippolytus* 1235-1240),¹² and Seneca the Younger (*Phaedra* 1080-1105),¹³ in the context of the Sclaveni in St. Caesarius of Nazianzus (*Four Dialogues* 2, 110)),¹⁴ the motive of praiseworthiness (in the context of the Veneti in Cassiodorus (*Variae epistulae* 12, 24)¹⁵ and Jordanes (*Getica* 29),¹⁶ in the context of the Sclaveni in Procopius of Caesarea in his description of Chilbudius (*Gothic War* 3, 14)),¹⁷ the motive of the wolf (in the context of statements about the Veneti in Strabo (*Geography* 5, 1, 9),¹⁸ while in statements about the Sclaveni in Georgius of Pisidia (*Heraclias* 2, 75)¹⁹ and elsewhere), etc.

Perhaps the most important of these common motives is the democracy (based on “sporadic” organization) which is demonstrated in relation to the Sclaveni in the famous description of Slavic democracy by Procopius (*Gothic War* 3, 14),²⁰ while in relation to the Veneti already half a millennium earlier in the statement by Silius Italicus in his *Punica*: “/.../ the Venetian

² Shipley 2011.

³ Kovacs 1995.

⁴ Fašalek 1964.

⁵ Migne 1862.

⁶ Duff 1934.

⁷ Whitby and Whitby 1986.

⁸ Jones 1917–1932.

⁹ Latte and Campbell Cunningham 2018.

¹⁰ O'Neill 1938.

¹¹ Smith 1860.

¹² Kovacs 1995.

¹³ Miller 2002.

¹⁴ Migne 1862.

¹⁵ Hodgkin 1886.

¹⁶ Mierow 1908.

¹⁷ Dewing 1914–1928.

¹⁸ Jones 1917–1932.

¹⁹ Bekker 1836.

²⁰ Dewing 1914–1928.

clans one and all /.../ declared that /.../” (*Punica* 12, 217–218).²¹ However, this sporadic democracy appears only in the case of the Veneti of pre-Roman epoch and the Sclaveni of the sixth century in the area North of the Danube’s lower stream, but not among the Veneti of Strabo’s description or the Sclaveni of Paul the Deacon, who speaks of a non-sporadic Slavene political entity (namely, a province), from which a conclusion about the difference between proto-Slavs, still characterized by sporadic organization, and proto-Slovenes, already organized in a non-sporadic manner – a result of Roman hegemonic influence –, has been derived.

Theoretical framework

Paradigms in studies of nations and nationalisms

Speaking of proto-Slovenes in Strabo’s time is nowadays considered problematic from the viewpoint of hegemonically established theories of nations. “Today’s prevailing and orthodox deliberation on nationalism is modernist /,” (Smith 2005, 67) explains Anthony Smith. “But it is not only nationalism that is modern. The same applies for nations, nation states, national identities and the whole ‘inter-national’ community” (ibid., 65).

The modernist theories are united by a claim, that nationalism rises as a process or transformation from the traditional to modern societies; some theories focus in detail on the spread of industrialization, while others on socio-economic, political and cultural conditions, which they find as a primary reason for the development and rise of nationalism (Mandelc 2011, 47).

In line with this, Gellner says that nationalism invents nations (Gellner 1965, 168); Hobsbawm explains, how this may be done through an ‘invented tradition’ (Hobsbawm and Ranger 1983), while Benedict Anderson deliberates on nations as modern ‘imagined communities’ (Anderson 1983).

But it had not always been so: “Prior to the Second World War many experts had supported the view that nations /.../ existed in all historical periods and that many nations exist from ancient times. This perspective may be called perennialism” (Smith 2005, 68). This was characteristic also for the Slovene historians, who had prior to the emergence of Peter Štih predominantly considered the Slovene nation as deriving directly from the period of the medieval state of Carantania. Štih argues that in the period of Carantania there were no differentiated Slavic languages nor had the modern Slovene language existed (Štih 2011), and so apparently takes a modernist view on the origin of the Slovenes, but in fact he only changes the referent in the perennial-primordial thought. He shifts from the Slovenes to the Slavs, and by doing so invents a tradition for the latter and pan-nationalizes the past, but nevertheless remains as his predecessors within the frame of perennial thought.

This paper is written within the framework of ethno-symbolism, which has established itself through the critique of both modernist and perennial theories. Perhaps the most important characteristic of ethno-symbolism is that: “By connecting the national identities with the previous ethnic ties and showing the influence of subjective dimensions of common symbols, myths, and memories, it explains the persistent power that modern nations have over so many people” (Smith 2005, 79). The characteristic of ethno-symbolism is also that it recognizes the status of a nation already in the antiquity to some peoples (to the Armenians and to the Jews), for whom not only a sense of difference from the outside people, but also the feeling of brotherhood within the collective was characteristic: “In these cases it makes sense to speak of nations in the ancient world, although carefully and to a limited extent, and to note beside the

²¹ Duff 1934.

more often pattern of ethnic states also the emergence of a new pattern” (ibid., 140). What follows is a finding, which in the light of Procopius’s description of democracy among the Sclaveni and the description of democracy among the Veneti by Silius Italicus, is of the highest significance: “Many modernists believe, that nations may only be found in democratic societies, as only in these societies can we speak of a mass citizenship” (ibid.).

Smith postulates ethnohistory as the one element that makes the national or ethnic identity transfer from generation to generation. He recognizes the coexistence of various narratives in the ethnohistory of an individual community; as an example, he highlights: “This was the case in Greece throughout the nineteenth century, when a classical Athenian version of Hellenism held by westernised intelligentsia and merchants was pitted against a Greek Orthodox popular ethnohistory which harked back to the medieval glories of the Byzantine empire /.../” (Smith 1999, 17).

Unfortunately, Smith doesn’t offer a theoretical model that sheds light on how one ethnohistoric representation among the two competing ones prevails over the other. But he does write a thought that may serve as the initiation to the conceptualization of this rivalry within the framework of hegemony: “Ethnic myths of descent figure prominently in the nationalist *Weltanschauung*. As a community of culture and a distinctive unity, the nation not only has a past, the roots of its unique identity must reside in its origins and genealogy” (ibid., 60-61). He adds:

The myths themselves /.../ are made up of several components, with differing sources, and they may well come to possess alternative meanings, and uses, for the various classes and status groups that comprise the ethnic community or nation. This is often a source of persistent conflict, so much so that the national tradition may be marked by a deep-seated cleavage based on rival concepts of identity /.../ (ibid., 62).

Hegemony

As is well known, Antonio Gramsci in his Prison Notebooks developed the (Lenin’s) term of hegemony into social science’s concept of political and cultural hegemony that includes the concept of the social class, and formulated hegemony as a set of prevailing norms and values through which the ruling class expands its worldview as natural, the only possible one, correct, true, useful to all, etc. and through it instead of by using mere coercion achieves the consent of the subordinate classes to the rule of these by them internalized and accepted norms that benefit only the ruling class and consolidate its rule.

In this sense the schools as the positive educational function and the courts of law as the negative educational function are the most important state activities: but really, many other, so called private initiatives and activities that form the apparatus of political and cultural hegemony of the ruling classes, strive to this same goal (Gramsci 1987, 131).

So, hegemony is not formed in the state administration in the narrower sense, but rather “/.../ hegemony is created in the field of ‘civil society’, parties and political groups, ‘ideological apparatuses’, such as universities, schools, and media, in intellectual circles, research institutes and ‘brain trusts’, in advertising agencies, and churches” (Hirsch 2014, 65-66).

Gramsci’s concept of hegemony was used by Stuart Hall, who offered a theoretical approach to the issue of how media messages (television news) are produced, distributed and interpreted (Hall 1973). He advocated the view that members of the audience play an active role at decoding the messages, as they rely on their own social context. He distinguished between the dominant or hegemonic type of decoding the text (news), and the oppositional or counter-hegemonic type (ibid.). The hegemonic type is a type the coder uses and expects the decoder to recognize and

reuse it. In this position the viewer accepts the meaning exactly as it was transmitted, since he is located within the frame of the dominant / hegemonic view (Gramsci's *Weltanschauung*). Contrary is the situation with the counter-hegemonic type of decoding: "It is possible for a viewer perfectly to understand both the literal and connotative inflection given by a discourse, but to decode the message in a globally contrary way" (ibid.).

As an example of the difference between the hegemonic and oppositional type of reading of a historical statement let's cite Ptolemy's record on the Veneti of European Sarmatia in the interpretation of Pleterški on the one hand and almost half a century older academic interpretation of the same phrase "*ethne megista oi te Oenedai*" of the ancient geographer on the other:

A) Hegemonic type of reading of Ptolemy: "The first more reliable messages about the Slavs originate from the 1st and 2nd centuries A.D. Pliny the Elder, Tacitus, and Ptolemy offer very deficient data about the Veneti, as they call the Slavs. The information is mainly limited to the reference of geographical location of Venetic tribes. The mentioned area encompasses **large space**, which reaches from the Carpathians along the Vistula to the Baltic Sea" (Babić et al. 1953, 1, 72).

B) Oppositional type of reading of Ptolemy: ".../ However, from the further context of his work it follows that the Veneti were populating a relatively **small area** East of the Vistula between the Gutones (Goths) and the Baltic Galindae and Sudavi next to the Bay of Vistula" (Pleterški 1990, 64).

Therefore, this paper uses the concept of hegemony to understand deliberations on the Veneti and the Slovenes / the Slavs. Namely, the theory of the medieval settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs cannot be considered a scientific theory. Were it scientific, it would have been founded on verifiable evidence. But there are no proofs for the settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs in the sixth century; there are no written sources from the sixth century that would report of this settlement, while the archaeological 'evidence' is circumstantial and unconvincing.

The theory of early medieval settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs cannot be considered as ideology either, although it spreads through the discourses on ethnogenesis of the ideological apparatuses of the state. Were we to consider this theory as ideology, we couldn't ever understand, why it was established in capitalism prior to World War II, in the era of German Nazi occupation, in the period of socialist self-management, and again in the transition to post-socialist capitalism.

The persistence of the theory of early medieval settlement of the Slovenes / the Slavs in such ideologically distant regimes, may only be understood through the concept of hegemony. Hegemony of the settlement theory is reproducing the existing production mode. This has – as Godina highlighted not long ago – not differed in the pre-war, post-war and post-independence period (Godina 2015). It was and still is all about the domestic productive mode. Patterns of colonization, plundering, incendiary culture, cooperatives etc., that the settlement theory sets up and through the ideological apparatuses of the state transmits to all as ours, pour via the 'spill-over effect' from the superstructure into the economy and sustain through generations the 'given' social-class relations. Here precisely is the point in forming the discourse of the autochthonic school in the science of ethnogenesis of the Slavs / the Slovenes (as is presented below):

The essential political problem for the intellectual is not to criticize the ideological additions, which are allegedly connected with science or to ensure to his own scientific practice the correct ideology, but in finding the possibilities of a new policy of truth.

/.../ It is not about emancipating the truth from each system of power /.../, but rather about separating the power of the truth from the social, economic, and cultural forms of hegemony, within which it operates today (Foucault 2008, 134).

Discussion – the Venetic theory

Statements about the Veneti

As a starting point to the analysis serves the understanding that the Baltic branch of the Veneti was identical to the Slavs, an understanding advocated by all relevant modern Slovene historians from Anton Tomaž Linhart to Bogo Grafenauer, respectively. Namely, beyond the Carpathians, in the alleged Slavic motherland of the allochthonous school, no ancient written source speaks of the Sclaveni, but only of the Veneti, and as a result – under the preposition that the Baltic Veneti were not a Slavic ethnic group – the Slavs would have disappeared from ancient literary sources.

Realizing that the ancient sources that speak of the Baltic Veneti indeed represent the ancient Sclaveni, it makes sense to analyze the Greco-Roman mythology, connected with amber (that was being brought to the Adriatic-Mediterranean area from the Baltic). Such an analysis undoubtedly shows that mythical figures or keywords, connected with amber, such as Phaethon, the Eridanus, Heliades, Hesperides, guinea-fowls etc., have been already in pre-Hellenistic period intertextually intertwined into a mythological network and anchored on the phenomenon of the Veneti. So, concerning the connection between amber and the Veneti the statement by Pliny the Elder that amber was being brought to the Adriatic area in the antiquity by the Veneti (*Natural History* 37, 11)²² is of the highest importance. Also important are the information by Pseudo-Scylax that the river Eridanus is located in the land of the Veneti (*Periplus* 19),²³ and a whole series of other statements from Alcman through Euripides to Strabo and others, from which it is beyond doubt shown that Phaethon's myth, be it in its classical amber version or be it in the version of Hesiod's Phaethon, was mythologically anchored to the phenomenon of the Veneti. Consequentially the relocation of an individual element of the Phaethon's myth in one statement, caused the relocation of the very Veneti in another. The replacement of the amber-Phaethon by Hesiod's Phaethon caused the movement in conceptualizations about the place of settlement of the Veneti from the Adriatic to Armorica (first done by Julius Caesar; *Gallic war* 3, 7-16),²⁴ as Hesiod's Phaethon is identical to Hesperus, which implies the West, unlike the amber-Phaethon, whose myth is connected to the Northern-European amber sites and to the Adriatic markets with this material on the other end of the ancient Amber trade route. Similarly, it was the relocation of the mythical river Eridanus, into which Phaethon falls, from the Northern-European area, where it is located by Hesiod (*Catalogue of women* fragment 40 A)²⁵ and Herodotus (*Histories* 3, 115),²⁶ to the area of the river Po, that drew with it the relocation of the settlement of the Veneti, who are first mentioned as living by the Po only by Polybius in the second century B.C., unlike the older statements about the Veneti that locate them on the Eastern shore of the Adriatic as done by Pseudo-Scymnus (*Periegesis* 188-194),²⁷ all the way to the Danube by Herodotus (*Histories* 5, 9),²⁸ and across it in the direction of the Baltic by Sophocles as quoted by Pliny the Elder (*Natural History* 37, 11).²⁹

²² Bostock and Riley 1855.

²³ Shipley 2011.

²⁴ Bohn and McDevitte 1869.

²⁵ Evelyn-White 1914.

²⁶ Sovre 2003.

²⁷ Müller 1855.

²⁸ Sovre 2003.

²⁹ Bostock and Riley 1855.

The following sources speak of the Baltic Veneti: Pseudo-Scymnus in his *Periegesis* mentions the Veneti closest to the Northern (Atlas's) pillar and adds that their settlement continues South of the Danube (“*entos Istron*”) all the way to the Adriatic (*Periegesis* 188-194),³⁰ and he also mentions the Veneti in Thrace (ibid. 387-391). Apollodorus of Athens in fragments of Strabo's *Geography* distinguishes between “coastal” and “inner” Paphlagonians (as he calls the Baltic and the Adriatic Veneti) and says that the former were unknown to Homer (*Geography* 7, 3, 6 and 12, 3, 26).³¹ Pliny the Elder in *Natural History* talks about the settlement area of the Veneti in the vicinity to the Cimbri, the Sarmatians, the Hirri and the Sciri (*Natural History* 4, 27),³² while on another spot he adds that it was the Veneti who were bringing amber to the Adriatic-Mediterranean area (ibid. 37, 11). Tacitus in *Germania* speaks of the Veneti on a vast area between the Peucini in the South and the Fenni in the North and adds that they are similar to the Sarmatians, but counts them among Germanic peoples because they live in permanent settlements (*De origine et situ Germanorum* 46).³³ Ptolemy in his *Geography* calls the Venedi “*ethne megista*” (major ethnos) and lists 15 peoples, who were living in European Sarmatia “under Venedi”; he also mentions the Venedic bay, which is his name of the Baltic Sea (*Geography* 3, 5).³⁴ Marcianus of Heracleia in the fourth century calls the same bay the “Vendic bay” (*Periplus of the Outer Sea* 2, 38),³⁵ named after the Western-Slavic people, called Wends. The itinerarium *Tabula Peutingeriana*³⁶ mentions the Veneti under the signifier Venadi Sarmatae next to the Baltic Sea, and again by the name Veneti between the Danube and the Dniester rivers. The poem *Widsith* speaks of the Veneti in the same breath as of the Gepids, which places them in the timeframe of the Gepid historiographic relevance between the fifth and the sixth centuries (*Widsith* 57-62),³⁷ while Jordanes in his *Getica*, as we have seen, equates between the Veneti and the Sclaveni, speaks of their war with Ermanaric in the fourth century and describes their settlement areas (*Getica* 5 and 23).³⁸

Beside these sources some sources refer to the Northern-European Veneti also by the signifier “Indi”, due to falling-off of the initial /v/ sound (Digamma) from the name “Vindi” (compare *Windisch*) in Greek or Greek-transmitted sources. Such is the case with some manuscripts of the already mentioned Marcianus's *Periplus of the Outer Sea*, where the “Vendic bay” is called “Indic bay” (*Indikon kolpon*). Similarly, both Pliny the Elder (*Natural History* 2, 67)³⁹ as well as Pomponius Mela (*De Chorographia* 3, 45)⁴⁰ speak of an event, when the Germans took some Indians, who became stranded in their land because of a shipwreck, as captives and then brought them to Rome. A people by the name Indii are mentioned in Europe also by *Laterculus Veronensis*⁴¹ in its appendix, called *Gentes*. The same signifier is found also at pseudo-Aurelius Victor, who says that the Indi sent legations to Rome during the reigns of Octavian and Antoninus Pius (*Epitome de Caesaribus* 1, 9 and 15, 4).⁴²

None of these sources says a single word about the alleged ethnic difference between these Veneti and the Adriatic Veneti, while as many as three of them (Pseudo-Scymnus, Apollodorus

³⁰ Müller 1855.

³¹ Jones 1917–1932.

³² Bostock and Riley 1855.

³³ Brodribb and Church 1868.

³⁴ Stevenson 1932.

³⁵ Schoff 1927.

³⁶ Miller 1887–88.

³⁷ Chambers 1912.

³⁸ Mierow 1908.

³⁹ Bostock and Riley 1855.

⁴⁰ Romer 1998.

⁴¹ Klein 1999.

⁴² Banchich 2000.

of Athens, and Pliny the Elder), some more, some less explicitly, beside Jordanes, express the view that the Northern-European Veneti were of the same ethnicity as the ones living South of the Danube. As these sources are independent from one another and as we know for a fact that the two branches of the Veneti were connected by the Amber path, we are allowed to conclude that they were indeed ethnically identical (or at the very least related), and had populated prior to Celtic invasions the whole area between the Adriatic and the Baltic. There are therefore only two possibilities: either both the Adriatic and the Baltic Veneti were Slavic, or neither of them was Slavic. In the case of the latter, the Slavs disappear from the ancient written sources, which is hardly imaginable for the continent's largest ethnic group, while in the case of the former the problem of the inscriptions of the Atestine archaeological culture, which were allegedly written by the Adriatic Veneti, arises.

This paper expresses the view that the Adriatic Veneti never extended to the area of the Atestine archaeological culture, as they were not mentioned there by anyone prior to Polybius, when the inscriptions of the Atestine archaeological culture had already gradually ceased to be written, while Polybius himself relocates them to the area – as has already been said – due to the relocation of the river Eridanus, which is connected in myth with the location of the Veneti. But if the area of the Atestine archaeological culture was not populated by the Veneti, who then did live there?

To find the answer to this question let's turn to the inscriptions of the Atestine archaeological culture. Slovene interpretations of these inscriptions, offered by Matej Bor, have been rejected by serious linguistic science for over thirty years. So, let's approach the inscriptions in a different manner and make an analysis of the ethnic and political collective names that appear on these inscriptions. It can be seen that the Venetic name appears only twice (on inscriptions Es 122 and Pa 3 bis), no more often than the name of the Romans that appears three times (Es 45, Es 49, Es 50) or of the Greeks, whose name appears twice (Es 76, Es II), the name of the Celtic tribe of the Boii that appears four times (Es 8, Es 28, Es 66, Es 127) or the name of the Vennonnes that appears twice (Pa 13), etc., while the name of Raetia appears as many as **31 times** (Es 24, Es 25, Es 26, Es 27, Es 30, Es 31, Es 32, Es 33, Es 40, Es 41, Es 42, Es 44, Es 45, Es 46, Es 47, Es 48, Es 49, Es 50, Es 51, Es 52, Es 53, Es 54, Es 55, Es 56, Es 57, Es 62, Es 64, Es 71, Es 73, *Es 125). Hegemony in Venetic scholarship claims that the entry "Reitia" is the name of the goddess, however this 'goddess' is not mentioned in relation to the Veneti (or at all) by any Greek or Roman literary source. It is possible that we are dealing with the goddess of the genus, for we know with certainty from a series of Roman sources that in the imperial epoch Raetia was a province (located in the Alps, where to, according to Pliny the Elder, the Raetians had migrated from the Po plain due to the invasion of the Celts; *Natural History* 3, 24).⁴³ We likewise know with certainty that the name "Reitia" was used as an identity (i.e. in subjective forms): as "Reitian" (Es, 49; male, singular), and "Reitiika" (Es 52, female, singular). The logical conclusion of the analysis of collective names on Atestine inscriptions is that these inscriptions were not written by members of one ethnicity only, as several collective names appear, and also that they were in majority written not by the Veneti, but rather by Raetians. We are therefore dealing with Raetian and not with Venetic inscriptions, which is exactly the reason why in Slovene (Venetic) these inscriptions remain largely non-understandable. To speak of Venetic inscriptions of the Atestine archaeological culture is therefore erroneous, it is a result of the invented tradition and nationalization of the past by the modern Italo-Venetic nationalism; it is hegemonic, and it should be abandoned by serious science.

⁴³ Bostock and Riley 1855.

With the emergence of Polybius's statement about the Veneti extending all the way to the river Po, which was taken up by Cornelius Nepos and after him by the emperor Octavian-August, and so the whole Rome, a tradition was started in which there was a duplication of the Venetic name. We are not dealing with one group of the Adriatic Veneti only, but with two of them. The sign Veneti was used as a politonym for (not only Slovene) population of Italy's region of Venetia (et Histria), and simultaneously as an exonymic ethnonym for a people living outside of (to the East of) this region and belonging to another language and culture (Slovene). This may also be seen from simultaneous listing of two groups of people, the Trojans and the Veneti, by Livy (*Ab Urbe Condita Libri* 1, 1),⁴⁴ which is repeated by Silius Italicus, however the locations are stated by him: Eugania of the Trojans, Aquileia of the Veneti (*Punica* 8, 602-604).⁴⁵ This duplication of the Venetic sign is especially well seen in the statement by Strabo, who speaks of the city Aquileia as standing outside of Venetic area (= Venetia), and who also speaks of a river, along which the (Eastern) border of Venetia is located, but at the same time, he speaks of (other) Veneti in the locality of the Corner of the Adriatic (the mouth of the Timava river), i.e., further to the East of Aquileia; that is further to the East of Venetia (*Geography* 5, 1, 8).⁴⁶

Statements about the Sclaveni

The Sclaveni are mentioned in the fifth century in Thrace by the Armenian writer Moses Khorenatsi (*Geography* 27).⁴⁷ In the seventh century the Eastern-Roman writer Theophylact Simocatta states that the Sclaveni were in the past referred to as Getae (*History* 3, 4, 7 and 7, 2, 1-6),⁴⁸ a name that appears in the Balkans already in Herodotus's epoch. The Sclaveni are mentioned by the name Getae in the early sixth century, definitely prior to the movement of the Langobards to Italy in 568, which allegedly triggered the Slavic expansion, also by Marcellinus comes (*Chronicon* 530).⁴⁹ Prior to the sixth century the Sclaveni are mentioned in the Balkans also by Constantine Porphyrogenitus, who does write about their expansion into Dalmatia from the areas North of the Danube, but already in the year 449 (*De Administrando Imperio* 29).⁵⁰ The Sclaveni are spoken of also by St. Martin of Braga in a list of peoples, which, beside the Sclaveni, only mentions the peoples populating Gaul between the 4th and the 6th centuries (*Ode to St. Martin of Tours* = IHC 00379a = ICERV 00349 = EDCS 38000031).⁵¹ Already in the fourth century the Sclaveni are described by St. Caesarius of Nazianzus, namely as living on "the same tract of land" as the people, called Phisonitae (*Four Dialogues* 2, 110),⁵² referred to after the biblical river Phison, which is equated with the Danube by Caesarius. Historiographic hegemony interprets as if the Phisonitae (and therefore also the Sclaveni) were living to the North of the Danube, which isn't so however, as we know from some manuscripts of the *Cosmography* by Julius Honorius that it was Roman Pannonia, which was considered as surrounded by the river Phison (*Cosmographia* 24).⁵³ Therefore, besides the Phisonitae the Sclaveni were populating Pannonia.

As the settlement area of the Sclaveni from Thrace through Pannonia and Dalmatia all the way to Gaul prior to sixth century thus corresponds with the settlement area of the Veneti, and

⁴⁴ Baker 1823.

⁴⁵ Duff 1934.

⁴⁶ Jones 1917–1932.

⁴⁷ Whiston and Whiston 1736.

⁴⁸ Whitby and Whitby 1986.

⁴⁹ Croke 1995.

⁵⁰ Tomašić 2003.

⁵¹ Šašel 1976.

⁵² Migne 1862.

⁵³ Riese 1878.

simultaneously the settlement corresponds also chronologically (there is no chronological gap between the Veneti of Julian the Apostate (*The Heroic Deeds of Constantius 71-72*)⁵⁴ and the Sclaveni of St. Caesarius of Nazianzus; both are mentioned in the middle of the fourth century in Pannonia), it becomes clear that they are the same nation, and not two different ones.

Should the analysis of the sources that mention the Sclaveni to the South of the Danube prior to sixth century not suffice, we can also list about 20 cases of the appearance of Slavene ethnonym in the Corpus of Latin Inscriptions (CIL). In some cases the name appears in archaic form with the letter T between S and L (Stlaborium instead of Sclaborum; Stlabon instead of Sclabon; Stlabia instead of Sclavia, etc.) due to the characteristics of archaic Latin, wherein the consonant set /stl/ stood in the same position as the younger set /scl/ (Lindsay 1894, 307). In other cases, however, such as the anthroponyms Sclavius Diogenes (CIL 06, 26012) or Marci Slavi Puteolani (CIL 16, 00009 = CIL 10, 07891), the record of the Slavic name on CIL is crystal clear and it proves the presence of the Sclaveni in the Roman empire already in the antiquity.

Administrative-political continuity of the Veneti and the Sclaveni

After the presence of Slavophone populations to the South of the Danube in the antiquity has been proven in the previous two sections, let's consider what were the political institutions of the Slavs / the Slovenes in the antiquity. There can be no doubt that the duplication of the sign Veneti, which we have already discussed above, was followed by administrative duplication of the Veneti, as such a conclusion arises from the document, called *Notitia Dignitatum*,⁵⁵ which speaks of two provinces of the Veneti: the first, called Venetia Inferior, and the second, called Venetia et Histria. The duplication of the Veneti follows from other texts also, among others two Venetias are mentioned by Zosimus (*New History* 5, 48).⁵⁶ Venetia inferior extended over the area of the former Atestine archaeological culture between the river Po and Aquileia, while the province Venetia et Histria extended over the Istrian peninsula and the area of today's Western Slovenia between Aquileia and the Atrans (Trojane) mountain. After the demise of the Western Roman empire and the establishment of Ostrogothic rule Istria became an independent province (*Variae epistulae* 12, 22),⁵⁷ but nevertheless two Venetias remained, as Cassiodorus (ibid. 10, 27; 12, 4; 12, 7; 12, 24) and also Jordanes (*Getica* 29; 42; 57)⁵⁸ keep on mentioning Venetia in plural. From this it follows, that after the making of an independent Istria the province "Venetia Superior" (not mentioned by any source), which extended to the North of Istria and East of Aquileia to the Atrans mountain, was established from the remainder of the former province Venetia et Histria. The question arises, to which of the two Venetias (Inferior, Superior) does Procopius's writing of a military engagement in Venetia in the year 549 between the forces of the Langobard Ildigis, who was in charge of an army, composed of 6 000 Sclaveni, and the forces of Eastern Rome, under the command of Lazarus (*Gothic War* 3, 35),⁵⁹ refer to? The historiographic hegemony claims that this battle occurred to the West of Aquileia, however as Venetia Inferior had already been under Frankish rule by 549, it seems a lot more realistic that it took place in Venetia Superior. It was thus freed from Eastern-Roman rule and was joined into the "province of the Sclaveni" (*Sclaborum provincia*) with the province of Pannonia Savia – through which Ildigis travelled to Venetia from the area of the Gepids, and where already Cassiodorus had mentioned the "ancient barbarians" (*Variae epistulae* 5, 14)⁶⁰ and Procopius

⁵⁴ Wilmer Cave Wright 1913.

⁵⁵ Fairley 1899.

⁵⁶ Green and Chaplin 1814.

⁵⁷ Hodgkin 1886.

⁵⁸ Mierow 1908.

⁵⁹ Dewing 1914–1928.

⁶⁰ Hodgkin 1886.

“the barbarians, who live a kind of brutish life and have no dealings with other men.” (*Buildings* 4, 5, 9).⁶¹ Jordanes, however, calls these barbarians between the city of Neviodonum (Drnovo pri Krškem) and the Mursian lake (next to the city of Osijek) by the name of the Sclaveni (*Getica* 5).⁶² That the Sclavene province was situated in Pannonia Savia and further to the West in Venetia Superior is confirmed also by an unlikely source, namely the Syriac Michael the Great, who in his *Chronicle* states that the land of the Slavs is located to the “West of the river Danube” (*Chronicle* 10, 21),⁶³ i.e. West of its Northern turn at today’s border between Croatia and Serbia, and not to the North of the Danube, as would have been expected had the migration scenario been correct. It is exactly because the Sclavene province was fought for under the leadership of the Langobard Ildigis that it is a Langobard source, Paul the Deacon, who first mentions it (*History of the Langobards* 4, 7).⁶⁴ The setting up of this province in the year 549 was followed by an invasion by the Sclaveni of the Eastern Roman empire from the direction of North-West that took place between 550 and 552 and was described by Procopius of Caesarea. A continuity between Slovene political entity of early medieval era with a nominally Venetic administrative unit of antiquity is thus determined.

Conclusion

So, the role of political sciences in the science of Slavic ethnogenesis has been established. The paper considers the relation between the classical Venetic theory and the allochthonous school in the representation of the origin of the Slovenes to be a relation of hegemony.

The year 549 is recognized as the breaking point in which the autochthonously considered Venetic-Sclavene nation set up the organizational frame of an independent military-political entity, called “*Sclaborum provincia*”.

This paper breaks the hegemony; it is a scientifically legitimate and long overdue act of paradigmatic counter-hegemony in the field of Slovene memory studies.

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⁶¹ Dewing 1940.

⁶² Mierow 1908.

⁶³ Yohanna Ibrahim 2009.

⁶⁴ Bradač et al. 1988.

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